

IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN FORMING THINKING AND SKILLS IN HISTORY LESSONS

Ochilov Iskandar Omongaldi oqli

Bachelor's degree student of Gulistan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7860244>

Abstract. *In this article, by using pedagogical technologies in history lessons, it is thought about directing students to perceive historical events, understanding their identity, concepts that help them grow as individuals, and educating them in the spirit of national and universal values.*

Keywords: *pedagogical technology, skills, skills, history science, thinking.*

INTRODUCTION

As human knowledge is not unlimited, it should not be forgotten that the methodology of history teaching, especially the types of history lessons, should be enriched with new options in the process of social development and scientific and technological revolution, and should be in a dialectical movement without standing in one place.

Currently, the social environment that surrounds the society leaves its mark on the students' outlook. In such conditions, the task of the history teacher is to draw the attention of all the students present in the class to them, using the differentiation method, while at the same time explaining the historical material that is acceptable for all of them, on the other hand, each student he should try to approach it individually, taking into account his interests. In order to improve the effectiveness of history lessons, the teacher should systematically monitor the development of history. Acquainting high school students with the content of new published works on history will increase their interest in studying history.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

In general, the use of educational techniques in history classes increases the effectiveness of the lesson. Technical tools serve to raise the quality of teaching and learning, to study the educational material with interest and mastery of the students. The most convenient for the teacher of the screen presentation is the slide film and the slides. It excels in coverage of historical events, variety of plotting, and wealth of visual material. The sequence of presentation of slides is determined by the teacher himself. Based on the footage, the teacher can tell a story, explain and conduct a conversation. If there are technical possibilities, two frames can be shown on the screen. In this case, for example, it is necessary to determine changes, for example, in the appearance of cities, changes in labor rates in different historical periods, and it will be possible to show and so on. Television broadcasts, movies can provide a lot of information in a short time. Through them, he can hear the live voices of the participants of historical events (performed by actors).

TV shows have a (topical) relevance compared to movies. Through them, especially the students get acquainted with recent events. Compared to these, the production of films itself takes a lot of time. Before showing the film to the students, the teacher himself should carefully review and study it. From educational films in history teaching experience. There are several ways of using it:

- a) the teacher connects his statement with showing the most important and bright pages of the educational film;
- b) a 10-14 minutes lesson is devoted to short educational films;

c) special film lessons are organized.

When a teacher introduces a movie clip or a TV show in a lesson, it is necessary to know their function in the educational process. Sophisticated and responsible, it is the adoption of movies, TV shows as the main source of knowledge on the subject, that is, in practice, it is called TV, that is, cinema neither the teacher nor the students should ignore it. Requires a lot of preparation how to screen students before class.

It is also good to be explained and prepared by telling them that they need information method. They had to do it while watching a movie (show). Assignments can be given. This includes questions about the film, making a plan (they will be written on the board). Readers should search for answers. During the looking such assignments are often given to high school students.

Correspondingly, the telescreen increases the effectiveness of instruction in history teaching. The experience of teaching history has proven that the tele class is ideologically, educationally and didactically more convenient and preferable than other instructional tools. Thus, the historical materials that should be kept in the memory of students constitute the second important component of historical knowledge. The teaching method means the methods of joint activity of the teacher and students aimed at achieving a certain goal in the educational process. In other words, teaching methods are both activities, i.e. arming students with knowledge, skills and abilities by the teacher, educating them from an ideological and moral point of view, forming a scientific worldview in them, and students includes the methods used in the activity of mastering the intended scientific knowledge, skills and competencies.

ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH RESULTS

The educational and educational significance of history teaching is also great. First of all, instructional tools serve as an important resource for students to learn. Guided images of historical facts and events reveals not only their appearance, but also their inner essence. Instructional tools help students understand complex historical events and the meaning of historical concepts more easily. Instructional tools help to form historical concepts, to better understand their theoretical conclusions and generalizations, objective laws of social development and interrelationships, and also serve as an important means of aesthetic education of students.

The process of knowing history begins with the acquisition of historical facts. The peculiarity of historical facts is that they never repeat themselves exactly. At the same time, students' learning of specific historical facts does not mean that they have mastered history. If there is no logical connection between the facts, then a simple set of facts formalizes knowledge and prevents the conscious assimilation of historical materials. Thus, in the process of studying history, the facts should not only be studied, but the necessary connections between them should be compared, defined and to some extent systematized. Historical facts can be of two types. First of all, some historical facts reflect a single event and occur only once in history under certain conditions, with the participation of persons of a certain period, in a strictly limited space and time. Secondly, historical facts reflect the characteristics of a certain historical period and time. In the process of searching for historical knowledge, students' thinking moves from the concrete to the generalized process, and again to the concrete, relying on the foundations of a somewhat higher level of knowledge. On the basis of this, the facts known to the student and their approach, as well as new facts discovered in connection with the development of the science of history, and the approach to physical evidence are rethought and gradually improved. This process is of great

educational and educational importance, especially today, when the Uzbek people have achieved their independence. In history education, transition from concreteness to generality and, vice versa, transition from generality to concreteness is not only a simple cycle, but also a process of continuous development of historical knowledge and mental maturity of students from simple to complex. In the formation of students' historical knowledge, the skillful guidance of the student's educational activities by the teacher is of particular importance.

Improving the effectiveness of history learning is mainly due to proper guidance of the educational process consists of, and this process mainly includes the following situations:

1. To provide students with historical sources of knowledge. Forming the main foundations and important aspects of historical knowledge sources for students on a scientific basis, first of all, the history teacher should acquire such knowledge theoretically and practically, as well as be armed with the optimal methods of conveying this knowledge to the minds of students. We need it.

2. To be able to direct the mental state of the students in relation to the historical material being studied, to actively awaken their interest in historical knowledge, to be able to organize strong and stable attention of the students during the lesson, and finally formation of independent thinking skills should occupy the main place in the work of the pedagogue.

3. The direct and systematic guidance of the teacher to the acquisition and understanding of historical knowledge by students during the lesson is one of the main conditions for a positive solution to this problem. In this place, the teacher asks the students to separately note the main (guiding idea, basic knowledge) issue of the subject being studied during the lesson, that is, the historical issue that they must know, if it is in the textbook, it is described in various notes. Specifies the preparation of the material, intonation if it is presented orally, the plan of the presentation of the topic, clearly indicating one or another direction on the map. The most important thing is that in this process, the teacher should activate the independent analysis of historical documents, periodical press, and works of fiction, regardless of whether students work on the text of the textbook.

4. The teacher should skillfully guide students' thinking at all stages of the process of learning historical material. This guidance should be the primary focus of the teacher when introducing new material, reinforcing it, completing homework and general review lessons. In particular, managing and managing students' cognitive thinking is of great importance in their mastery of theoretical issues. The goal observed here is for students to draw clear theoretical conclusions from the complex of knowledge they have acquired from historical facts, to have the opportunity to independently interpret the theoretical expression of historical facts.

5. In order to strengthen the knowledge of students, it takes a special place in the organization of guiding their activities in class and homework and in the formation of historical knowledge in them.

6. Checking the students' educational activities and making changes to them. Including not only the knowledge they have acquired, but also their ability to think about historical knowledge, as well as their worldview. It should be expressed in the perception and management of the extent to which they master their concepts, their ability to work independently with historical materials, their knowledge gained from history in the process of reading, and especially in their everyday social life. The role of thematic planning of history lessons, curriculum and manuals, and textbooks should be noted in the acquisition of historical knowledge in the process of learning history.

CONCLUSION

By way of conclusion, it is extremely significant to be able to use historical facts and knowledge clearly and in the necessary form and methods. Uzbekistan's independence, historians, historians - method and experienced history teachers tested the textbooks of Uzbekistan and world history at the level required by our time by means of experiments, and spiritually educated the school youth. Aims to create scientifically-methodically and didactically complete textbooks that ensure their development.

REFERENCES

1. Ishmuhammedov J.G. Education with the help of innovative technologies ways to increase efficiency. Tashkent, Science-2007.
2. N. Atayeva, M. Salayeva, S. Khasanov. General pedagogy. - T.: "Science and technology", 2013.
- A. Sa'diyev Teaching the history of the peoples of Uzbekistan. T. "Teacher". 1993. 53 – p.
3. History of the Middle Ages (V - XV centuries). Khrestomatia, V.Ye. Stepanova, A. Ya. Shevlenko. M. 1989. 60 - p.
4. Kadirova Gulhayo. Formation of students' historical knowledge main components of the process. (in the example of "World History" lessons).